

Year of Open Science Culminating Conference. March 21-22, 2024. Online
<https://www.cos.io/yos-conference>

Title: Open Science for Academic-Supported Community-Led Research
Presenters: Nathan Morrow (Tulane University)

Although open science promises greater inclusion and diverse participation, a search of the code-hosting platform GitHub reveals a striking lack of participation in open source projects in the southern United States. The Gulf Coast states (Louisiana, Alabama, Mississippi, Florida and Texas) also struggle against pervasive socioeconomic disparities including inequity in environmental justice, health, and other vulnerabilities. Access and use of data is one of the greatest challenges to advancing EJ action. NASA can provide an improved evidence base to advance underserved EJ communities as they struggle with air quality, localized flooding, climate change-related extreme events, and disaster resilience. This represents a significant opportunity to engage underserved communities and environmental justice organizations with diverse and supportive academic partnerships to advance open science for climate, environmental, and ocean justice with NASA data and NASA Transform to Open Science (TOPS) resources. Advancing Gulf Coast Environmental Justice Leadership & Engagement in Open Science (AGEJLE-OS) will (re)convene community-engaged academic-supported EJ networks to 1) to obtain certification badges in open science; 2) facilitate collaboration on open science projects that use NASA Earth Science data to address pressing climate and environmental justice priorities in the Gulf Coast States and 3) strengthen proposal development capacity for community-led academic-supported research.